

IMPORTANCE OF MARRIAGE AND TIME OF MARRIAGE

J. Haresh* & Dr. K. Jothimani**

* Research Scholar, Registered Number: UP18G9961005, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies (Vistas), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

** Research Supervisor, School of Vedic Astrology, Vels Institute of Science, Technology & Advanced Studies (Vistas), Pallavaram, Chennai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: J. Haresh & Dr. K. Jothimani, "Importance of Marriage and Time of Marriage", International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 7, Issue 2, Page Number 1-8, 2022.

Abstract:

Marriage is a relationship of man and woman which is recognized by custom and Law and involves certain rights and duties in the case of both the persons entering the union. Family is formulated by marriage, as two people get married. Even more it is the sexual pairing of male and female activity that is the pinnacle of the creative process. Astrologer can make astrology prediction for marriage. When can people get it, why marriage happens at a very young age and why marriage gets delayed? Some Dosha, such as Mars Dosha, Punarphoo Doaha and some combination of malefic planets causes delay marriage or no marriage. Hindu predictive Astrology enables one to time and predict evens with considerable accuracy, by Vimshottari or Udu Dasa system and transit of planets. Horoscopes in respect of early marriage, late marriage, too late marriage and no marriage are explained with illustrations.

Key Words: Marriage, Family, Creative, Age of Marriage, Planets, Bhava, Punarphoo-Dosha, Dosa Samiyam, Vimshottri-Dasa, Transit Of Planets, Time Of Marriage.

Introduction:

Marriage is a sacrosanct union of all our enterprises, the most serious one is our marriage. This world itself will be a heaven or a hell depending on one's state of married Life. Marriage is a legally and socially sanctioned usually between man and a woman. It is regulated by laws, rules, customs and briefs. The universality of marriage with in two different societies and cultures is attributed to the many basic social and personal functions for which it provides structure such as sexual gratifications and regulation. Marriage in India is between two families, rather two individuals arranged marriages. Most of the parents approach the astrologer for only getting the predictions regarding their boys' and girls' marriages at their adolescent age. Contribution of astrology to the world as it can foresee any problems in the life of anyone through their Horoscope. Astrology can precisely determine which area the problem shall root from. Some of the details that can be getting from Astrology prediction for marriage include whether native of the Horoscope will get married. If so when can the native expect it, why marriage at very young age, why marriage gets delayed and unmarried yogh etc. All these facts are discussed in this article.

Important of Marriage:

Marriage is more important than any other institution one is capable to form in this life, at it is not individual's happiness only, but that of others also, which is affected by their conduct in it. It has been ordained for the protection of society from foul and immoral acts on the one hand and continuance of the chain of society itself each other. Marriage is a relationship of man and woman which is recognized by custom and Law and involves certain rights and duties in the case of both the persons entering the union.

Relationship of Man and Woman:

Creation of male and female is not an accidental fact or after thought but the very apex of God's creative activity. Even more it is the sexual pairing of male and female activity that is the pinnacle of the creative process. To deny the distinction of two sexes is to deny what is integral to God's ultimate creative act.

Family and Society:

Family, as an institution, is to be found even in the most primitive of human societies in the world. The Vedic word "Dampatti" denoting jointly the husband with wife, etymologically means the joint owners of house. A family is a community of people living together in an environment which is center of heading, a place where one can live, where one can admit one's frustrations, stupidities and anger to people who do not have to relative. The family is by far the most important institution in society. Family is formulated by marriage, as two people get married, by form a family which moves further, and get benefit and give benefit to society. It includes relation between parents and their children and also extends to grandparents. The family disintegrates when the marital relations break, as in the case of divorce. Historically it has been transformed from a more or less self-contained unit into a definite and limited organization of minimum size, consisting primarily of the original contracting parties. It is a unit of Society. Society to state and state to nation.

Age for Marriage in the Previous Centuries:

In the previous centuries population in India was Low. The needs of people were also minimum. They lived a simple and happy life. They lived in the joint family system with unity of love and satisfaction. Most of marriages took place at a young age of boys and girls. Particularly girls were married at the young age of 8 years old, before they attain puberty. "Silappathikaram" a great epics in Tamil language, mention that a boy got

married at his age of 16 years and a girl at her age of 12 years. Dr. A. Ramakrishnan, author of text book in Tamil “Thamizhaga varalarum Thamizhar panpadum”¹ said that was no reference for the age limit for marriage in ancient period of “Sanga Kalam”. Father of our nation, Mahatma Gandhi said in his autobiography with regret that he married at his age of 13 years. After on enactment of marriage act-1955², in India, the age of marriage for woman has been fixed as 18 years and for men at the age of 21 years of old. However in some Communities, child marriages are still being practiced implicitly.

Age of Marriage in the Modern India:

Professor. Dr. Pulippani Sundaravaradhachariyar, author of the text book “Jothida Sakalathikaram”³ explained about age of boys and girls for marriage in the modern India. Now a days joint families have disappeared and individual nuclear families have appeared. It takes more time to procure status and save money for their life needs. Then the requirements are minimum. There was a tendency to live with satisfaction. Now modern necessities like T.V., fridge, car etc have become the basic necessities. After getting marriage the couple has increased their desire to buy a house, flats, etc, by adjusting their income. Therefore adolescence is spent for studying higher education, then searching a good job with more salary. If income is not sufficient, wife also have to go to job. For such kind of many reasons, marriages get delay and take place between the ages of 21 to 25 years of old for when and 25 to 30 years of old for man. Therefore age of marriage can be divided in three categories for this century.

- Early marriages: Marriage held between age of 21 years and 27 years old.
- Late marriages: Marriage held between age of 28 years to 33 years old.
- Too late marriage: Marriage held above age of 34 years of old.

Time of Marriage tells Astrology:

Marriage is an important event that gets a paradigm shift to the life journey of every person. Since the happiness, success and other important aspects of life ultimately depend on the marriage and the life partner, everyone looks the marriage with great expectations. Here is now astrologer can make astrology prediction for marriage. So of the details that people can get from astrology prediction for marriage include people get it, if so, when can people expect it, why marriage happens at a very young age and why marriage gets delayed.

Brihat Parasara Horo⁴:

Maharishi Parasara explained time of marriage in his text book “Brihat Parasara Horo”

- If yuvati Lord (7th Bhava Lord) is in a benefic’s Bhava (sign), while venues is exalted, or is in own sign, the native will marry at the age of 5 or 9.
- If sun is in yuvati, while his dispositor is yuti with venus, there will be marriage at 7th or 11th year of age.
- Venus in Dhan (2nd Bhava) while yuvati (7th) Lord is in Labh(11th Bhava) will give marriage at the age of 10 or 16.
- Marriage will take place during the 11th year if Venus is an angle from Ascendant, while ascendant lord is in Capricorn or Aquarius.
- The native will marry at 12 or 19, if Venus is in an angle from the Ascendant, while Saturn is in yuvatic counted from Venus.
- Should venues be in yuvati from moon, while Saturn is in yuvati from Venus, marriage will be in the 18 years.
- Marriage will be in the 15th year, if Dhun Lord (2nd Lord) is Labh (11) will bring marriage 13 years after birth.
- One’s 22nd /27th year will confer marriage if Venus is in Yuvathi(7) from the 8th Bhava (ie., Dhan(2) from Ascentant). While depositor is Yuti with Mars.
- Should yuvati Lord be in Vyaya (12) while the natal Lord is in Yuvati in Naramsa, marriage will be in 23rd/26th year of age.
- Either the 25th year, or the 33rd year will bring marriage if Randhr (8th Bhava) Lord in yuvati, as Venus is in Naramsa Ascentant.
- Should Venus be in Dharm (9th house) from Dharm (9th house) while Raghu is in one of the said Bhavas (ie in Putr-5 or Dharm-9) marriage will take place during 31st or 33rd years.
- The native will marry at 30 or 27, if Venus is in Ascendant while 7th Lord is in yuvati itself.

Many points about the age of marriage, mentioned in “Brihat Parasava Horo” are not applicable now. Marriage is to be adapted according to chronological, custom of the nation and current Act of marriages.

¹ Thamizhaga varalarum Thamizhar panpadum - Dr. A. Ramakrishnan,

² HniduMmarriage Act-1955

³ Jothida Sakalathikaram - Dr..Pulippani.Sundaravaradhachariyar

⁴ Brihat Parasara Horo - Maharishi Parasara

Marriage Related Bhavas (House Signs) in Astrology:

By marriage, it is meant that one more member is added to the family which is indicated by the second house. This addition is on an agreement which is denoted by seventh house and such an additional member brings permanent tie of friendship for pleasure and progeny, shown by the 11th house. That is why houses 2, 7, and 11 are examined and to find out whether-

- Marriage is promised or not;
- The description of the partner; whether already related or not, his or her features, characteristics, profession etc.
- State of married life:
 - Whether it is a harmonious one promising an inseparable temperament
 - The couple any attachment, simply to maintain the prestige of the family, Manage to live in the same premises
 - To lead the life like cat and rats especially during day time, even though the couple may become the parents of many children
 - To be going on marrying and divorcing.

Important Combinations on 7th House Drawn from the Classical Astrology Text Books:

Important combinations on the seventh house (indicating the life Partner) drawn standard and authoritative works, are given below.⁵

- The 7th Bhava reckoned from the Lakna or the moon be occupied or aspect by the 9th Lord, or Sign Lord or other benefits, marriage will be happy and the wife, a loving and fortunate woman.
- The 2nd, 7th, and 11th Lord in Kendras (Quadrants 1-4-7-10 houses) or trikonas (trines 1-5-9 houses), aspect by Jupiter can ensure a happy marriage and a fertile wife.
- If benefices are placed in the 2nd, the 7th and the 11th houses from 7th Lord, the wife or husband will be able to derive all happiness with healthy and lucky children.
- If Mars and Saturn are in the 7th in Capricorn, the wife is chaste, beautiful and lucky.
- If the 7th lord and Venus are in even Signs, if 7th house is also an even sign or otherwise weak, the person will have a good wife and children.
- If Jupiter occupies the 7th house, the native or own vargas or has attained “Gopura or vaiseshikamsa” the wife will be good and beautiful.
- If the 7th house be a benefic sign or if Venus as 7th Lord be aspect by a benefic planet, the wife or husband will be devoted and charming.
- If 7th Lord is in the 5th or 5th Lord is in the 7th, the native not Marry, as if he gets married, childless.
- When the 2nd and 7th houses in the case of men and the 7th and 8th houses in the case of woman are occupied or aspect by Malefic, the loss of wife or husband happens.
- If the 5th or 8th Lord in the 7th, death of wife or husband occurs.
- Malefic in the 12th, 7th and Ascendant with the weak moon in the 5th deny marriage of children.
- If the moon and Venus are in opposition of Mars and Saturn, marriage is denied.
- The moon and Saturn in the 7th in a woman’s chart indicates remarriage while in a man’s chart, the deny marriage or progeny.
- Malefic in the 2nd, 7th and 8th from Lakna result in demise of married partner.
- The sun and Rahu in the 7th cause loss of wealth through women.
- Mercury in the 7th in Taurus or Jupiter in the 7th in Capricorn or Saturn and Mars in 7th in Pisces are injurious to the life of the married partner.
- Mercury and Ketu in Lakna give a sickly wife.
- Saturn and Mercury in the 7th indicate a widow or widower for a life partner.
- If a strong moon be in the 7th, the wife will be good.
- Ketu in the 7th gives a shrew for a wife while Rahu gives an outcast woman.
- If the 6th, 8th and 9th houses be conjoined with Malefic and be also aspect by Malefic, the wife of the native will indulge in adultery
- If Saturn is in the 7th, or if the Lord of the Naramsa occupied by the 7th Lord be a malefic, or if the 7th Lord or Venus be in depression Rasi or Naramsa, the wife will be a wicked woman
- If weak and afflicted Venus be in the 7th house the wife maybe barren or the husband may be impotent.
- If Mars with a Malefic occupies the 7th house, the native may suffer impotency caused by urinary problems.
- If Saturn in a Watery sign occupies, the 6th and 12th houses and devoid of benefic aspects, the native will be eunuch.

⁵ How to judge a horoscope – B.V.Raman

Marriage – Punarphoo⁶: (Moon + Saturn)

Whenever Saturn has got any connection what-so-ever with moon, there will be same obstacle or impediment, not only during negotiation but also at the time of fixation and even at the time celebration of the marriage. This connection between moon and Saturn causes delay, though ultimately both of them do much more good with better partner.

Mars and Marriage:

Mars occupying 1,2,4,7,8,12 houses (signs) counted from Lagna, moon and Venus is said to cause “Mars Dosha”. One may ask why should Mars be considered to be evil only when it occupies 1,2,4,7,8, or 12th position from Lakna or Moon, or Venus. Is it a benefic when it occupies any of the other signs. Now, we are considering about the results, Mars during the period of fixation of marriage, the time of celebration and sate of marriage life. We do not judge whether it is favorable or not for other considerations in life such as finance, fortune, profession etc. We can concern with the health of couple, harmony among them and happiness to them.

- Lagna or ascendant denotes health, Longevity and personal characteristics. As Lagna will be the 7th (Maraka) house to the 7th which indicates partner, Lagna also indicates (the maraka) or the end of life of the partner.
- The second house denotes the family happiness or otherwise in domestic life, increase or decrease in the number of members of the families by marriage, by birth or death of children etc. Further, second house is the 8th to the 7th and it shows the danger and the difficulties to the partner.
- The fourth house denotes domestic environments. The sages have declared that evils occupying a sign which is either four or eight from a Bhava, spoil the Bhava. Hence Mars in 4 is evil too ascendant, i.e. to the health and belonging of the native.
- The seventh house shows the legal bondage and the wife or husband, her or his health, longevity of both and also the characteristics of the partners, whether they will have good understanding among themselves or not. Hence the position of Mars in 7, is not conducive to the above benefits.
- The eighth house shows the difficulties of the native and the finance and fortune of the partner, as well as their longevity.

Eighth house is called ‘Mangalya Sthana’ i.e. the duration of the married life. Mars situated in this house is therefore evil.

- The twelfth house indicates the real pleasure which the partners derive, the deception, the loss etc. Further, sages have declared that the house 3,6,10 and 11 are “Upachaya Sthanas” and Malefics by nature occupying any of the Upachaya Sthanas will produce desirable results.

Again let us consider the following, suppose Lagna indicates your residence, then houses 2 and 12 are the neighboring houses and how can one have peace if these are occupied by wicked persons. If the bad fellow were to be in just the opposite house i.e., the 7th then also there is danger for the native. As already mentioned not be occupied by evil planets, if good health, happy domestic environments and a long spell of pleasant wedded life are to be enjoyed.

Dosha Samyam: (Cancellation of Dhosham)

Regarding Mars Dosha, there are various rules expanded in “Devakerala” and “Jataka Chandrika”⁷ that the evil effect on Mars will be nullified. Mars may be in 1,2,4,7,8 or 12 houses from Lakna or moon or Venus. If it is in mesha or virichika own signs, there is no Dosha. Mars in Venus signs cannot harm if its 12th house. Mars in Mercury signs will have its results warded off if it is in 2nd house. Mars has no Dosha in the houses owned by sun, Moon and Saturn. Evil results of Mars cannot operate if sign occupied by Mars is ruled by Jupiter and happens to be 8th. If Mars occupies its own or its exalted sign or debilitated sign and if those signs happen either the 4th or the 7th counted from Lagna, moon and Venus, the evil results of Mars will be warded off. It is said that Mars in 1 or 2, or 4, or 8 or 12 if conjoined with or aspect by either Jupiter (Guru) or Mercury (Bhudha) loses its evil results.

Match Horoscopes with Mars Dosha:

Now let us consider how to match horoscopes how to match horoscopes having Dosha and fix up the marriage.

- If in the bride’s chart, there is Mars dosha, select such a bridegroom who also has more or less similar Mars Dosha.
- If in the bride’s chart, there is Mars Dosha, due to its relative position counted from lagna or moon or Venus and there is ‘Parihara’ or motification due to some disposition or conjunction with modifying planet or aspect by a benefic, match it with that of the bride groom in whose chart also there is the dosha of Mars and also the modification.

⁶ Marriage and Married life and children – Jyothish Marthand.K.S.Krishnamurti.

⁷ Jataka Chandrika –Saraswathi Mahal Thanjaur

- If there is no dosha at all in the bride's chart and it is termed as "Suddha Jadhagam", match it with one which has no dosha at all.

Similarly there are three group in Mars Dosha.

- There is dosha in the chart without any modification.
- There is dosha in the chart with modification.
- There is no dosha at all.

It is therefore, necessary that Astrologers should carefully weigh and consider and various points of Mars Dosha in the given charts and advises on the correct match.

Time of Marriage arrives by Vimshottari (Udu) Dasa:

Astrology has achieved remarkable success in the matter of timing events, as to when the different indications of Horoscope – marriage birth of children, financial gain and losses, access to wealth, loss of reputation. Increase of fame death of parents and many other events occurring in our lives would fructify or happen. Hindu predictive Astrology enables one to time and predict events with considerable accuracy, by Vimshottari or Udu Dasa system. There are several methods suggested for timing marriage in classical works. The lord of the sign occupied by the 7th Lord or that the sign occupied by the 7th Lord in Navamsa are capable of giving marriage in their Dasas. Venus the Karaga or natural significator of the seventh house, and the moon can do also give marriage in his Dasa. The Lord of the 7th house, if he associates with Venus, can also give marriage in his Dasa or bhukti (sub periods of Dasa). The 2nd Lord of the ruler of the sign occupied by the 2nd Lord in Navamsa is also capable of conferring marriage in his Dasa. The Lords of the 9th and 10th houses are empowered to give marriage in their Dasas if the earlier Dasas are fruitless. Marriage is also possible in the period of planet with the 7th Lord or the planet occupying the 7th house.

Another method is to add the longitude of the Lords of the Lagna and 7th House. When Jupiter from it the resultant Rasi or its trines, it is favorable for marriage. The resultant obtained by adding the moon's longitude to that of the 7th Lord or its trines when transited by Jupiter can also give marriage. Although there are several enumerated as marriage causing planets in their periods, due consideration must be paid to delay caused by other factors. Saturn's aspect on the 7th house and 7th lord both from lagna and the moon and on Venus delays marriage, if the Dasa lord is not very strong. The association or aspect of the Lord of the 6th, 8th or 12th on the 7th house, 7th lord and Karaka also rules out early marriage.

Transit of Jupiter and Marriage:

According to the study of Astrology Jupiter is an influential and benefic planet. It is a planet of knowledge, which has its influence on, mind soul, education, marriage and wealth etc. Jupiter has different impact on individuals according its transit in different houses as per their birth chart. Marriage can take place when Jupiter, transit the 2nd, 5th, 7th and 11th houses calculated from Lagna and moon sign in the birth chart.

Primary Importance Must be Given to the Natal Positions and Dasas and Only Secondary Consideration to Transiting Planets:

1. Early Marriages:

In most cases, early marriage happens due to the influence of benefic planets on the ascendant and 7th house. Benefic planets like Jupiter, Venus, Moon, Mercury will always help giving the individual an early marriage. Malefic planets like Mars, saturn, Rahu, Ketu and a malefic Sun would always delay the marriage. Malefic planets make us work hard towards getting anything and always tend to delay the result. There are many combinations that give rise to an early marriage. These combinations should be seen in both the D1 and the D9 (navamsa) chart. If these combinations occur in both the charts then the probability of an early marriage increases. The various combinations are

- Moon in the ascendent or the 7th house. Moon is a very fast moving planet and gives quick results for marriage when placed in these 2 houses, provided it is unafflicted by malefic planets.
- Mercury in the 1st/7th house in D1(Rasi) or D9(Navamsam) chart. Mercury is also a very fickle minded planet like the moon, it makes the individual impatient and hence they tend to get married early. This mercury should be direct and unafflicted to give an early marriage. A retrograde mercury in the 7th would not give an early marriage.
- 7th Lord is placed 5endra to the 7th house (7th lord in 7th, 10th, 1st or 4th house) gives an early marriage.
- 7th lord is exalted/in its sign., 5) 7th house is free from malefic aspects
- 7th house is free from 'Paap Katari' yoga. (No malefic plants in the 6th and 8th house)
- Venus is in its own sign/exalted, free from any malefic influence and should not be combust.
- Venus and Jupiter are placed Kendra to the 7th house.,9) Unafflicted Venus in the 7th house.
- 7th lord is conjunct Venus.,11) Jupiter in 1st /7th house or aspecting the 7th house.

Some other combinations for early marriages:

Venus moon in 7th house (without malefic aspects),Mercury moon in 7th house, Exalted Venus in 7th house, Jupiter moon in 7th house, Mercury Venus in 7th house

Example 1:

The following chart is that of a boy who got married at the age of 22 years old.

Date of Birth: 19-5-1956

Time of Birth: 03-30 P.M.

Place of Birth: Uttiramerur

Birth Star: Uttiraphalguni (Uthiram -2- patham)

		Sun Mercury Kethu	Venus	Jupiter		Mercury Kethu	
	RASI			Jupiter		NAVAMSAM	
Mars							Lagna Saturn
	Saturn Raghu			Lagna Moon		Raghu	Mars

Balance of Sun Dasa at birth is 03-years, 00-month, 22 days.

Lord of Lagna, Mercury is in the 9th house with sun and Kethu. 7th house is Pisces. No planet is occupying the 7th house. Jupiter is aspects the 7th house. The lord of 7th house Jupiter is in the 11th house. Jupiter occupies his exalted sign Cancer. In Navamsa, Jupiter is Pushkaramsam (Pisces). Kalathra karaka, Venus as 2nd and 9th Lord is beneficially disposed in friendly sign in a quadrant. Therefore, Lagna, 7th house, and Kalathrakaraka and favorably disposed. The native got marriage at his age of 22 on 07-07-1977, during the period of Raghu Dasa and Raghu Bukthi. Raghu is aspected by Jupiter, Lord of Seventh house.

Late Marriage:

Late marriage happens due to the influence of malefic planets on the 7th house/ 7th lord or Venus. The various combinations for a late marriage are:

- Direct Saturn in the 7th house or if 7th lord gets conjunct Saturn
- Venus Saturn conjunction (within 7 degrees)
- 7th house is in paap kartari (malefic planets in 6th and 8th house)
- Rahu, ketu, Mars and Saturn are aspecting 7th house/7th lord or sitting in the 7th house
- Venus is heavily afflicted (with malefic planets like rahu. ketu Saturn or mars)
- Venus gets combusted by sun (within 5 degrees)
- No benefic aspects on the 7th house or 7th lord
- 7th lord gets debilitated or is placed in an enemy sign
- Malefic sun in the 7th house
- If the ascendant gets occupied by Rahu, ketu, malefic sun, mars or Saturn
- Saturn is aspecting the 7th house
- 7th lord is placed in the nakshatra of saturn
- Cancer and Leo ascendants can naturally have a late marriage because of the influence of Saturn on the 7th house
- 7th lord gets combusted by sun.

Some other combinations for late marriage:

Mars and Saturn in 7th house, Sun and mercury in 7th house, Sun and mars in 7th house, Rahu mars / Rahu Saturn / Rahu sun in 7th house, Sun saturn in 7th house, Retrograde Venus/ Jupiter/ Mercury in 7th house, Ketu mars/ ketu sun/ ketu saturn in 7th house, and 7th lord goes in 6th /8th /12th house

Example 2:

The following chart is that of boy who got married at the age of 34 years old.

Date of Birth: 23-01-1946.

Time of Birth: 04-15 PM.

Place of Birth: Arcot

Birth Star: Hustham

			Raghu Mars Saturns	Sun Venus		Lagna Moon Kethu	Mars Saturn
	RASI				NAVAMSAM		
Venus sun							
Lagna Mercury Kethu		Jupiter	Moon	Mercury	Raghu Jupiter		

Balance of moon Dasa at the time of Birth is 06- years, 09- months, 19- days.

The Lord of Lagna, Jupiter is in 11th house from Lakna. Lakna is occupied by, the 7th and 10th lord of Mercury and Kethu. 7th Bhava is occupied by Raghu, Mars and Saturn. 7th house is afflicted by the three malefic planets. Kalathrakaraka, Venus as 6th and 11th Lord is in 2nd house with sun and aspect by Mars. Kalathrakaraka Venus is also afflicted. Hence late marriage happens due to the influence of malefic planets on the 7th house, 7th Lord and Venus.

However the 7th Bhava is aspect by Lord of Lagna Jupiter from the 11th bhava. Only Jupiter's aspect on the 7th house has prevented a complete affliction of malefic planets in the 7th house. The native got marriage at his age of 34 on 30-4-1999, during Jupiter Dasa Jupiter Bukthi.

Example 3:

The following chart is that of man who got married at the age of 45 years old.
 Date of birth: 22-02-1976. Time of birth: 10-15 P.M. Place of birth: Chennai.
 Birth Star: Anuradha

Jupiter	Kethu	Mars		Jupiter	Raghu Venus	Mercury	
Sun	RASI			Saturn	NAVAMSAM		
Venus Mercury				Saturn			
	Moon	Lakna Raghu		Lagna Sun	Moon	Kethu	Mars

Balance of sani dasa at the time of Birth 03- years, 07-months, 04 days.

The lord of lagna, Venus as 1st and 8th Lord is in the fourth house with mercury. Venus and mercury are aspect by Saturn and afflicted. 7th house, Aries is occupied by kethu and aspect by Saturn. The lord of 7th house (Aries), Mars is in 8th house. As mars is in 8th house, it makes "Ankaragha Dhosha." The Kalathrakaraka Venus is in 4th house. Venus is aspect by Saturn. 7th Bhava, Lord of 7th Bhava and karaka Venus all are afflicted severally.

Therefore, the marriage is too delayed. In the Navamsa, Jupiter who is in his own house has got "vargothma" and Pushkaramsam. The lord of seventh house, Mars is in Mercury Navamsa. The benefic Jupiter aspect the Saturn. 12th house and 2nd house are also aspect by Jupiter. Only Jupiter's aspects have prevented a affliction of Malefic planet. The native got married at his age of 46 on 09-09-2021 during Venus Dasa and Mercury bukthi.

No Marriage:

There are so many combinations in Vedic Astrology, one of the illustrated Yoga in classics is "Sadhu Yoga" in which person remains unmarried or divorced, lives separated life or she is having no pleasures of marriage and married life. Since our stars controls our life in various manner, similarly our birth map indicates about the happiness from marriage, if good aspects and healthy state of planets are present in chart then these aspects assures the lifelong happiness in married life

Pravrajya (Sanyasa) Yoga⁸ (Asceticism):

Pravrajya Yoga is explained in the classical texts "Phaladeepika" of Manthreswara. When four or more planets with Sun and Moon conjoins in Kendra or Trikona houses leads to the formation of Sanyasa, Sadhu or Asceticism Yoga. This Yoga inclines the native towards renunciation or to give up the worldly pleasures even any relation. Some combinations ascribed in classical texts are:

Four or more than four Planets when conjoins in any house, if this conjunction is in the Kendra or trikon houses then it gives strong Asceticism or Sanyasa.

When Lords of lagna, 4th, 10th, and Mars is also in a mutual aspect then it gives Asceticism or Sanyasa.

When moon is in strong position along with lagna and lagna lord are strong together.

Benefices in 3rd 6th from Arudha Lagna gives Asceticism.

Significator planets – Jupiter and Venus should also be considered to assess the delay of marriage.

Here are some other combinations for unmarried:-

- If 7th lord having association with 6th 8th 12th houses or their Lords.
- Malefic present in 7th house or having malefic aspect on 7th house.
- 7th lord debilitated or combust
- Papa katri yoga for 7th house or 7th lord.
- 7th house or 7th lord is on Rahu Ketu axis
- Presence or aspect of cruel or paapi planets to the 7th hose like, Rahu Ketu Shani Mars causes delay, separation or native may remain unmarried for the long time.

Example 3:

The following chart is that of man who has no marriage.
 Date of birth: 29-10-1960. Time of birth: 11-42 P.M. Place of birth: Mayiladuthurai
 Birth Star: Sathayam.

		Mars		Kethu	Mars		Jupiter
Moon Kethu	RASI			Lagna	NAVAMSAM		
				Mars			

⁸ Phaladeepika - Manthreswar

		Raghu	Sun
Saturn Jupite	Mercury Venus	Sun	Venus Saturn
			Lagna Raghu

Balance of Raghui dasa at the time of Birth 07- years, 03-months, 12 days.

Lagna is Cancer. Lord of Lagna the Moon is in the 8th bhava with Kethu and aspect by Saturn. The Lagna lies between Mars and Raghu in the papa katri yoga. Lord of 7th bhava Saturn is in 6th bhava with Jupiter the lord 6th. The both 7th bhava and 7th lord Saturn are aspect by the malefic Mars from the 12th bhava. Mars and Saturn aspecting mutually. The family bhava(2nd) is occupied by Raghu and lord of the 2nd bhava Sun has gone to Libra its debilitation. and become weak. Kathrakaraka Venus is in the house of Mars in both Rasi and Navamsam. Further Venus is in the star of Saturn and with Mercury the lord of 12th bhava, The lagna, 7th Bhava, Lord of 7th Bhava and karaka Venus all are afflicted severally. Hence the marriage is not promised to the native of the horoscope till date.

Conclusion:

Of all our enterprises, the most serious one is marriage. Queries about marriage and life partner are most frequently asked to an astrologer. The Vedic astrology has very good techniques, through which we can predict marriage of a person easily. Marriage compatibility is an important contribution of astrology to the world, as it can foresee any problem root from in the married life of a men and women and can precisely determine which are shall the problem root from. We can get an idea about Time of Marriage in astrology. Astrology foretells, and helps to the people whether the marriage is promised but it come off late in life. Whether the married life will be happy or unhappy. Astrology if used properly will tell peoples those movements of life and where they should put their focus to enjoy life to fullest.

References:

1. Dr. A. Ramakrishnan, "Thamizhaga Varalarum Thamizhar Panpadum", Ilakkiya Pnnai Mdurai
2. Dr. Pulippani. Sundaravaradhachariyar, "Jothida Sakalathikaram", Sri Ananda Nilaiyam, Chennai
3. Maharishi Parasasarar. Translated in English by Dr. S. P. Bhagat, "Brihat Parasara Horo", Books on Google Play
4. Kalidasar. Translated in Tamil. By S. Krishnamurthy Sasthri, "Jathaka Chandrikai", Saraswathi Mahal Thanjavur
5. B. V. Raman, "How to judge a horoscope",
6. Manthreswara. Translated in English by P. B. Pillai. "Phaladeepika", Jyotirivas, Sasthamangam Trivandram